

Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of 2-(6'-Chlorobenzothiazol-2'-ylamino)-4-[N⁴-{N¹-(n-butyl)sulphanilamido}]-6-(arylthioureido)-s-triazine Derivatives

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Thiazoles are known to exhibit antiinflammatory¹, antitubercular² and bacteriostatic activities. Triazinylthiourea derivatives are found active as bactericidal, fungicidal and herbicidal agents³ and thiourea derivatives possess wide therapeutic activities⁴.

Expecting that the combined presence of N-C=S and thiazole groupings in an *s*-triazine nucleus may enhance antibacterial activity, we have synthesised some 2-(6'-chlorobenzothiazol-2'-ylamino)-4-[N⁴-{N¹-(n-butyl)sulphanilamido}]-6-(arylthioureido)-*s*-triazines (3).

2-Amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole was prepared according to literature method⁵. Cyanuric chloride and 2-amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole were condensed in equimolar proportions to give the intermediate 1. Compound 1 was reacted with sulphanilamido-n-butane to give intermediate 2 which was further reacted with various arylthioureas to obtain the corresponding *s*-triazine derivatives (3).

Experimental

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

2-(6'-Chlorobenzothiazol-2'-ylamino)-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine (1): To a stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (1.84 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone at 0–5°, a solution of 2-amino-6-chlorobenzothiazole (1.84 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone was added. The reaction mixture was stirred at 0–5° for 2 h maintaining neutral pH. It was then poured on to crushed ice and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from alcohol, (90%), m.p. 297°d.

2-(6'-Chlorobenzothiazol-2'-ylamino)-4-[N⁴-{N¹-(n-butyl)sulphanilamido}]-6-chloro-*s*-triazine (2): To a stirred solution of 1 (3.32 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone at 35°, was added a solution of sulphanilamido-n-butane (2.28 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone over a period of 0.5 h. The temperature was then gradually raised to 45° during 2 h with stirring and maintaining neutral pH. It was then poured on to crushed ice and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from alcohol, (74%), m.p. 138°.

2-(6'-Chlorobenzothiazol-2'-ylamino)-4-[N⁴-{N¹-(n-butyl)sulphanilamido}]-6-(arylthioureido)-*s*-triazine (3). General method: A mixture of 2 (5.24 g, 0.01 mol) and arylthiourea (0.01 mol) in acetone was refluxed for 3 h on a water-bath. It was then treated with crushed ice and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from alcohol. All compounds (yield 49–65%) in general exhibited ν_{max} 800 (C₆N₃), 3300–3310 (NH), 1480–1490 (C–N thiourea), 1150 (S=O sulphonamide) and 1670 cm⁻¹ (C=N conjugative cyclic); 3a (R=C₆H₅), m.p. 179°d; b (R=*o*-CH₃, C₆H₄), 161°, ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 2.73 (ArCH₃), 4.0 (C–N thiourea), 7.4 (ArH), 5.3 (NH aromatic ring), 7.9 (NH benzothiazole); c (R=*m*-CH₃, C₆H₄), 181°; d (R=*p*-CH₃, C₆H₄), 151°d, δ (CDCl₃) 2.72 (ArCH₃), 4.0 (NH–CS–NH), 7.3 (ArH), 5.4 (NH aromatic ring), 7.9 (NH benzothiazole); e (R=*o*-Cl, C₆H₄), 111°d; f (R=*m*-Cl, C₆H₄), 159°d, δ (CDCl₃) 4.2 (NH–CS–NH), 7.4 (ArH), 5.4 (NH aromatic ring), 7.9 (NH benzothiazole); g (R=*p*-Cl, C₆H₄), 154°d; h (R=*o*-NO₂, C₆H₄), 129°; i (R=*m*-NO₂, C₆H₄), 122°; j (R=*p*-NO₂, C₆H₄), 166°. All compounds showed satisfactory N analysis.

Compounds 3a–j were screened for their antibacterial activity⁶ against *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, *P. vulgaris* and *S. paratyphi* B. at a concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹ in acetone. All the compounds showed moderate activity (zone of inhibition maximum 2.0 mm) against all the organisms when compared with the standard drugs ampicillin (5.0 mm), erythromycin (6.0 mm), gentamycin (6.0 mm), penicillin (6.0) and chloramphenicol (6.0 mm).

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